

SUPPLEMENT 3. Information of the collections used for Phylogeny 3. Those collections sequenced in this study are in bold. Unavailable items are indicated with -. Holotypes, epitypes and neotypes are indicated by HT, ET and NT, respectively.

Genera	Species	Collections	Origins	GenBank Accession Nos.				References
				ITS	nrLSU	<i>tef-1a</i>	β - <i>tub</i>	
Ingroup								
<i>Parasola</i>	<i>Pa. aporos</i>	RC-F92.191 (HT)	France	MK397584	MK397604	-	-	Malysheva <i>et al.</i> (2019)
	<i>Pa. aporos</i>	CL-F09.005	France	MK397586	MK397606	-	-	Malysheva <i>et al.</i> (2019)
	<i>Pa. auricoma</i>	NL0087	Hungary	JN943107	JQ045871	FM897236	FN396252	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2010)
	<i>Pa. auricoma</i>	CNF1/4718	Croatia	OQ842767	OQ842768	OQ850152	OQ850168	Pošta <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Pa. cinnamomescens</i>	LAH37773 (HT)	Pakistan	OQ779055	OQ779058	-	-	Khan <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Pa. cinnamomescens</i>	LAH37775	Pakistan	OQ779057	OQ779060	-	-	Khan <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Pa. cinnamomescens</i>	LAH37774	Pakistan	OQ779056	OQ779059	-	-	Khan <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Pa. conopilea</i>	CBS325.39	Netherlands	MH856033	MH867531	-	-	Vu <i>et al.</i> (2019)
	<i>Pa. conopilea</i>	CNF1/5310	Croatia	OQ845887	OQ845888	OQ850154	OQ850170	Pošta <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Pa. crataegi</i>	SSt08-154 (HT)	Germany	KY928605	-	-	-	Szarkándi <i>et al.</i> (2017)
	<i>Pa. crataegi</i>	NL-4175	Hungary	KY928603	KY928631	-	-	Szarkándi <i>et al.</i> (2017)
	<i>Pa. cuniculorum</i>	K(M)191984 (HT)	UK	OL630105	-	-	-	Schafer <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	<i>Pa. cuniculorum</i>	CNF1/5143	Croatia	OQ848756	OQ848757	OQ850156	OQ850172	Pošta <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Pa. galericuliformis</i>	NL-6601	Hungary	FM163187	FM160722	-	-	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2009)
	<i>Pa. galericuliformis</i>	NL-0095	Sweden	FM163188	FM160721	-	-	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2009)
	<i>Pa. galericuliformis</i>	NL-0466	Hungary	FM163192	FM160717	-	-	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2009)
	<i>Pa. galericuliformis</i>	NL-0288	Sweden	FM163193	FM160716	-	-	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2009)
	<i>Pa. glabra</i>	LAH-SHP-5 (HT)	Pakistan	KY461717	KY621806	KY461735	-	Hussain <i>et al.</i> (2018)
	<i>Pa. glabra</i>	HUP-SHP-23	Pakistan	KY461718	KY621805	-	-	Hussain <i>et al.</i> (2018)
	<i>Pa. haizhuensis</i>	HKAS145963 (HT)	China	PV155174	PV147348	PV156693	PV156731	This study
	<i>Pa. haizhuensis</i>	HTBM2191	China	PV155175	PV147349	PV156694	PV156732	This study
	<i>Pa. hercules</i>	Ulj10.8.1984 (HT)	Netherlands	HQ847027	HQ847112	-	-	Direct submission by Nagy <i>et al.</i>
	<i>Pa. kuehneri</i>	Ulj31.5.1987 (HT)	Netherlands	KY928608	KY928633	-	-	Szarkándi <i>et al.</i> (2017)
	<i>Pa. kuehneri</i>	CNF1/4334	Croatia	OQ849153	OQ849154	OQ850157	OQ850173	Pošta <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Pa. lactea</i>	NL-0283	Hungary	JN943113	JQ045887	FM897239	FN396248	Direct submission by Nagy
	<i>Pa. lactea</i>	NL-0288	Hungary	JN943106	JQ045872	FM897233	FN396250	Direct submission by Nagy
	<i>Pa. lilatincta</i>	NL-0468a	Hungary	FM163200	FM160709	-	-	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2009)
	<i>Pa. lilatincta</i>	NL-0281	Hungary	FM163197	FM160712	-	-	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2009)
	<i>Pa. lilatinctoides</i>	LAH-SHP-8 (HT)	Pakistan	KY461722	KY461725	KY461731	-	Hussain <i>et al.</i> (2018)
	<i>Pa. litoralis</i>	K(M)264814 (HT)	Cyprus	OL630108	-	-	-	Schafer <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	<i>Pa. litoralis</i>	DJS20130125001	Cyprus	OL630107	-	-	-	Schafer <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	<i>Pa. malakandensis</i>	HUP17501 (HT)	Pakistan	KP738713	KU599829	KU599831	-	Hussain <i>et al.</i> (2017)
	<i>Pa. malakandensis</i>	CNF1/8698	Croatia	OQ849158	OQ849167	OQ850158	OQ850174	Pošta <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Pa. megasperma</i>	Orton4132 (HT)	UK	OL630101	-	OL630935	-	Schafer <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	<i>Pa. megasperma</i>	CNF1/5704	Croatia	OQ849166	OQ849224	OQ850159	OQ850175	Pošta <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Pa. misera</i>	NL-0280 (NT)	Hungary	FM163210	FM160699	-	-	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2009)
	<i>Pa. misera</i>	NL-0677	Hungary	FM163211	FM160698	FM897240	FN396249	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2009)
	<i>Pa. nudiceps</i>	Orton 4133 (HT)	UK	OL630102	-	-	-	Schafer <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	<i>Pa. nudiceps</i>	CNF1/4804	Croatia	OQ849230	OQ849229	OQ850160	OQ850176	Pošta <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Pa. nudiceps</i>	NL-3621	Norway	JN943134	JQ045875	-	-	Direct submission by Nagy

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SUPPLEMENT 3. (continued)

Genera	Species	Collections	Origins	GenBank Accession Nos.				References
				ITS	nrLSU	<i>tef-1a</i>	β - <i>tub</i>	
	<i>Pa. nudiceps</i>	NL-3167	Sweden	JN943136	JQ045865	-	-	Direct submission by Nagy
	<i>Pa. papillatospora</i>	CNF1/7858 (HT)	Croatia	OQ862770	OQ862755	OQ850164	OQ850179	Pošta <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Pa. papillatospora</i>	NL-2952	Hungary	HQ847028	HQ847113	-	-	Direct submission by Nagy <i>et al.</i>
	<i>Pa. parvula</i>	CAL1667 (HT)	India	MH379796	MH393599	-	-	Ganga & Manimohan (2018)
	<i>Pa. plicatilis</i>	NL-0075 (ET)	Hungary	FM163214	FM160695	-	-	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2009)
	<i>Pa. plicatilis</i>	NL-0284	Hungary	FM163189	FM160720	FM897235	FN396251	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2009)
	<i>Pa. plicatilis-similis</i>	NL-2125 (HT)	Sweden	KY928620	-	-	-	Szarkándi <i>et al.</i> (2017)
	<i>Pa. plicatilis-similis</i>	CNF1/5484	Croatia	OQ850018	OQ850017	OQ850166	OQ850180	Pošta <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Pa. psathyrelloides</i>	CAL1753 (HT)	India	MK682756	MK682754	-	-	Ganga & Manimohan (2019)
	<i>Pa. psathyrelloides</i>	AMH10119	India	MK682752	MK682759	-	-	Ganga & Manimohan (2019)
	<i>Pa. pseudolactea</i>	HUP-SU-412 (HT)	Pakistan	KY461719	KY621799	KY461733	-	Hussain <i>et al.</i> (2018)
	<i>Pa. pseudolactea</i>	HUP-SU-413	Pakistan	KY461720	KY621800	KY461734	-	Hussain <i>et al.</i> (2018)
	<i>Pa. schroeteri</i>	L:C.B.Ulje1140	Netherlands	KY928628	-	-	-	Szarkándi <i>et al.</i> (2017)
	<i>Pa. schroeteri</i>	Dahncke1502	Germany	KY928616	KY928635	-	-	Szarkándi <i>et al.</i> (2017)
	<i>Pa. setulosa</i>	Maruyama14.7.1999	Hungary	HQ847030	HQ847115	-	-	Direct submission by Nagy <i>et al.</i>
	<i>Pa. setulosa</i>	HMJAU46367	China	MW822929	OL376319	-	-	Direct submission by Zhu <i>et al.</i>
Outgroup								
<i>Coprinopsis</i>	<i>Cp. calospora</i>	CBS61291 (HT)	Netherlands	GQ249275	GQ249284	GQ249268	GQ249259	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2011)
	<i>Cp. udicola</i>	AM1240 (HT)	Germany	KC992967	KC992967	KJ732831	KJ664922	Örstadius <i>et al.</i> (2015)